

1 **Methyltransferase control of Xist activation by Dnmt3b.**

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7 We report here control of Xist activation by the *de novo* DNA methyltransferase Dnmt3b. Dxz4 locus
8 encoded transcripts and the non-coding RNA FIRRE that controls Xist imprinting center activation
9 topologically were also notably influenced by expression of *DNMT3B* or its mutation found in ICF.

10 Citations

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